

Total syntheses of sesquiterpenes and diterpenes involving aryl participated cyclisations

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A brief review is provided of the recent syntheses of sesquiterpenes and diterpenes accomplished in the author's laboratories which serve to underscore the synthetic power of aryl participated cyclisations. The methodology is concerned principally with (a) intramolecular anionic cyclisation of phenols, and (b) acid-induced aryl participated cyclisation of diazomethyl ketones.

Syntheses of bridged tricyclic sesquiterpenes involving aryl participated cyclisations of indane derivatives

Sesquiterpenes occupy a conspicuous place in the domain of terpenoids because of their wide occurrence, unique structural features and important biological activities. These represent different structural and stereochemical patterns involving ring systems comprising three to eleven carbon atoms. Sesquiterpenes occur as mono-, bi-, tri- and tetracyclic systems and quite often with various types of oxygenated functionalities. Consequently, the complexity of structural framework incorporating therein several asymmetric centres in a compliment of fifteen carbon atoms has stimulated research in this field from structural, mechanistic and synthetic aspects. In order to develop convenient methodologies for the synthesis of bridged carbocyclic systems encountered in tricyclic sesquiterpenes, investigations were initiated in the laboratories of Organic Chemistry, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Calcutta, in the early sixties. A total synthesis of the bridged tricyclic hydrocarbon (\pm)-clovane (1) was reported¹ by Dutta and co-workers as early as 1965. Later, Venkateswaran and co-workers accomplished² a total synthesis of the tricyclic sesquiterpene (\pm)-isoclovane (2). In continuation of this programme, synthetic studies were undertaken by the present author to evolve suitable methodologies for entry into the carbocyclic framework of several bridged tricyclic sesquiterpenes. The synthetic efforts involving aryl participated cyclisations of indane derivatives as the key reactions have culminated in successful total syntheses of the bridged tri-

cyclic sesquiterpenes pseudoclovane-B, isolongifolene, Δ^2 -cedrene, isokhusimone, khusimone and zizaene.

Aryl participated cyclisations of indane derivatives to generate specifically functionalised tricyclic ring systems related to natural products are relatively unexplored. The utilisation of indane derivatives for the synthesis of bridged ring systems related to tricyclic sesquiterpenes offer a number of important strategic and tactical opportunities. The aromatic rings of the indanes are inert to a wide range of reaction processes and may, therefore, be carried out unchanged through protracted sequences. At the same time, they can be an excellent source of latent functionality. Indane derivatives are often crystalline and have better than average stability.

Total synthesis of (\pm)-pseudoclovane-B :

Bridged tricyclic sesquiterpenes derived from acid treatment of caryophyllene and caryolan-1-ol possess novel skeletal features and have attracted considerable attention as challenging synthetic targets. Total syntheses of the tricyclic sesquiterpene isoclovane (2), a product of dehydration of caryolan-1-ol with polyphosphoric acid (PPA), and

clovane (3), an acid induced rearrangement product of caryophellene, have been reported²⁻⁴ by several groups of workers. Pseudoclovane-B (4), another sesquiterpene incorporating a tricyclo[6.3.1.0^{1,6}] dodecane framework, was isolated and characterised⁵ along with 2 and several other sesquiterpenes when caryolan-1-ol was treated with polyphosphoric acid. The structure 4 of pseudoclovane-B was con-

clusively established through X-ray crystallographic analysis⁶ of the corresponding dibromide. For a total synthesis of (\pm)-pseudoclovene-B (**4**), we envisaged that intramolecular anionic cyclisation (Ar_1-6 cyclisation)⁷ of the indane derivative **5** would provide the dienone **6** as a potential tricyclic intermediate (Scheme 1). The dienone **6** is suitably functionalised for conversion to pseudoclovene-B (**4**) requiring only stereoselective reduction of the Δ^5 -bond and introduction of a *gem*-dimethyl group at the site of the carbonyl group.

The bromophenol **5**, easily prepared⁸ from 2-methyl-5-methoxyindan-1-one, was subjected to the sequence of reactions (**6** \rightarrow **11**) (Scheme 1) leading to the first total synthesis⁸ of (\pm)-pseudoclovene-B (**4**). Ar_1-6 cyclisation of **5**

Scheme 1

using *t*-BuOK as the base provided **6** in high yield. Catalytic hydrogenation (H_2 , 10% Pd/C) of **6** proceeded stereoselectively to give the *cis*-fused ketone **7** as the sole product. The conversion of **7** into the corresponding trimethylsilylcyanohydrin derivative followed by treatment with $POCl_3$ and pyridine afforded a mixture of the unsaturated nitriles **8** and **9**, in which **9** was the major product. Alkylation of this mixture with MeI in the presence of LDA (1 equiv.) and HMPA (1 equiv.) followed by chromatography furnished the crystalline alkylated nitrile **10** in 40% overall yield. Reduction of **10** with diisobutylaluminium hydride followed by Huang-Minlon reduction of the resulting aldehyde **11** afforded (\pm)-pseudoclovene-B (**4**). The identity of synthetic **4** was confirmed from 1H and ^{13}C NMR spectral studies and DEPT experiments.

The transformation of the tricyclic ketone **7** into dihydropseudoclovene-B (**15**) was accomplished⁹ as shown in Scheme 2. Condensation of **7** with ethyl cyanoacetate provided the unsaturated cyanoester **12** to which MeMgI was added to give the ester **13** from which the acid **14** was obtained. Treatment of **14** with $Pb(OAc)_4$ and iodine fol-

lowed by reduction of the resulting product with zinc dust and acetic acid furnished (\pm)-dihydropseudoclovene-B (**15**). Catalytic hydrogenation of **4** also provided the same dihydrocompound **15**.

Scheme 2

A highly efficient stereocontrolled total synthesis of (\pm)-pseudoclovene-B was accomplished¹⁰ using aryl participated *ortho*-cyclisation of the indane derivative **16** as the key step (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3

The bromophenol **16** was prepared¹⁰ from 2,5-dimethyl-7-methoxyindan-1-one using a straightforward sequence of reactions. Ar_1-6 cyclisation of **16** in the presence of *t*-BuOK (1 equiv.) provided the dienone **17** in excellent yield. Catalytic hydrogenation (H_2 , 10% Pd/C) of **17** furnished the *A/B* *cis*-fused ketone **18** in near quantitative yield. Bromination of **18** followed by dehydrobromination of the resulting α -bromoketone afforded the enone **19**. Conjugate addition of $LiMe_2Cu$ to **19** in the presence of $BF_3 \cdot Et_2O$ provided the saturated ketone **20**. The same saturated ketone **20** was also obtained¹¹ through conjugate addition of $LiMe_2Cu$ to **17** followed by catalytic hydrogenation. The tosylhydrazone derivative of **20** was treated with MeLi to give (\pm)-pseudoclovene-B (**4**) in high yield.

Total synthesis of (\pm)-isolongifolene and (\pm)-isolongifolene-4,9-dione :

The well-known sesquiterpene longifolene undergoes rearrangement in the presence of acid to provide an isomeric bridged tricyclic sesquiterpene known as isolongifolene (**21**). On the basis of chemical and spectroscopic studies, the struc-

ture **21** was proposed¹² for isolongifolene by Dev and co-workers and this structure was confirmed by Sobti and Dev by a synthesis¹³ of isolongifolene (**21**) from camphene-1-carboxylic acid (**22**). Later, Piers and Zbonzy reported¹⁴ a formal synthesis of (±)-isolongifolene. The total synthesis of isolongifolene presents a formidable challenge in view of the difficulty associated with the construction of tricyclo[6.2.1.0^{1,6}]undecane ring system with *gem*-dimethyl groups in two of the three rings and an isolated double bond

in ring A. We have successfully employed an Ar₁-5 cyclisation strategy to accomplish a very convenient and efficient total synthesis of (±)-isolongifolene¹⁵. A synthesis of (±)-isolongifolene-4,9-dione (**23**) has also been achieved using aryl participated intramolecular cyclisation of an indane derivative as the key step (*vide infra*).

Our synthesis of isolongifolene (**21**) from the indane derivative **24** is outlined in Scheme 4. Treatment of **24** with silver benzoate in methanol in the presence of triethylamine

Scheme 4

furnished the ester **25** which was converted into the bromophenol **28** through the intermediates **26** and **27**. Intramolecular anionic cyclisation (Ar₁-5) of **28** in the presence of *t*-BuOK (1 equiv.) provided the dienone **29** in high yield. The construction of the bridged tricyclic framework of isolongifolene was thus accomplished in a highly satisfactory manner. Regioselective conjugate addition of LiMe₂Cu to **29** in the presence of BF₃·Et₂O furnished the

crystalline enone **30** which was converted into the thioketal **31**. Desulfurisation of **31** was accomplished very efficiently with sodium and ethanol in liquid ammonia to give (±)-isolongifolene (**21**). The structure of **21** was confirmed through comparison of ¹H NMR spectrum with that of an authentic compound.

For synthetic entry into the bridged ring system of isolongifolene by an alternative route, acid-induced intramolecular cyclisation of the diazoketone **24** was investigated. This indeed proved to be a remarkably facile process. Thus, a brief treatment of **24** with trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) at -20° afforded the dienedione **32** in excellent yield. Conjugate addition of LiMe₂Cu to **32** in the presence of BF₃·Et₂O furnished (±)-isolongifolene-4,9-dione (**23**) in 60% yield (Scheme 5).

Scheme 5

The diazoketone **24**, the key intermediate in the present synthesis of **21** and **23**, was prepared from the known ester **33** as shown in Scheme 6. Treatment of **33** with an excess of MeMgI followed by intramolecular cyclisation of the re-

Scheme 6

sulting carbinol with PPA provided the tetrahydronaphthalene derivative **34** which on oxidation with CrO₃ yielded the ketone **35**. The formyl derivative of **35** was treated with alkaline H₂O₂ followed by CH₂N₂ to give the diester **37**. Dieckmann cyclisation of **37** furnished the β-ketoester **38**.

Reduction of **38** with NaBH_4 followed by catalytic hydrogenolysis afforded the ester **39**. The corresponding acid **40** was converted into the diazoketone **24** using a standard procedure¹⁶.

Total synthesis of (\pm)- Δ^2 -cedrene :

Tricyclic sesquiterpenes isolated from cedar wood oil and vetiver oil have attracted intense attention as challenging synthetic targets. The isomeric sesquiterpenes α -cedrene (**41**)¹⁷ and Δ^2 -cedrene (**42**)¹⁸, isolated from cedar wood oil and vetiver oil, respectively, incorporate tricyclo[5,3,1.0^{1,5}]

undecane framework but differ in the position of a double bond and in relative stereochemistry of the respective secondary methyl group. The total synthesis of these tricyclic sesquiterpenes presents an interesting problem in view of the presence of four asymmetric centres and an isolated double bond in one of the rings. Although α -cedrene has been synthesised¹⁹ a number of times, the synthesis of Δ^2 -cedrene was not known in the literature. We have for the first time accomplished²⁰ a stereocontrolled total synthesis of (\pm)- Δ^2 -cedrene (**42**) using an aryl participated cyclisation strategy (Scheme 7). The bromophenol **48** required for the intramolecular cyclisation was prepared from 3,3-dimethyl-7-methoxyindan-1-one²¹.

Scheme 7

Michael reaction of the indanone with methyl crotonate

followed by hydrolysis afforded the keto-acid **43** as a diastereoisomeric mixture which was converted into the enol lactone **44**. Catalytic hydrogenation of **44** furnished a single acid **45** which was converted into the bromophenol **48** through the intermediates **46** and **47**. Ar¹-6 cyclisation of **48** provided the tricyclic dienone **49** in high yield. Catalytic hydrogenation of **49** furnished the A/B *cis*-fused ketone **50** (96%), the stereostructure of which was established by X-ray crystallography. The hydroxymethylene derivative of **50** was treated with alkaline H_2O_2 to give the diacid **51**. Pyrolysis of the barium salt of the diacid **51** yielded²² the tricyclic ketone **53**. The same ketone **53** was also prepared through Dieckmann cyclisation of the diester **52**. Treatment of **53** with MeMgI and subsequent dehydration furnished a 4 : 1 mixture of the hydrocarbons **42** and **54**. The isomerisation of **54** to **42** was effected efficiently by treat-

ment with *p*-toluenesulfonic acid to give (\pm)- Δ^2 -cedrene (**42**) in high overall yield. The identity of synthetic **42** was secured through ¹H, ¹³C NMR, IR and microanalytical data.

Total synthesis of zizaane sesquiterpenes :

The zizaane sesquiterpenes isolated from the essential oil of vetiver varieties are characterised by the tricyclo[6.2.1.0^{1,5}]undecane ring system and zizaane (**55**) is the parent hydrocarbon of this family. (–)-Khusimone (**56**), a tricyclic ketone, is one of the main olfactively important constituents of vetiver oil which undergoes acid-catalysed isomerisation²³ to (–)-isokhusimone (**57**). Liu and Chan²⁴ converted khusimone (**56**) into zizanoic acid (**58**).

Zizaane sesquiterpenes have been the subject of considerable synthetic activity since 1968. A successful synthetic approach to this class of natural products must address three principal problems : (i) the construction of the tricyclo[6.2.1.0^{1,5}]undecane ring system, (ii) installation of an exocyclic methylene unit, and (iii) control of the stereochemistry, particularly the *trans*-fused hydroindan ring junction. The first total synthesis of (\pm)-isokhusimone (**57**) was reported by Buchi and co-workers²⁵ who also synthesised (\pm)-

khusimone (**56**) from (\pm)-isokhusimone in two steps. A synthesis of (\pm)-isokhusimone (**57**) from norcamphor has been accomplished recently by Burnell and Wu²⁶. Synthesis of (–)-khusimone has been reported by Liu and Chan²⁴, Oppolzer and Pitteloud²⁷ and Sakurai and co-workers²⁸. Total synthesis of (\pm)-zizaene has been reported by Deljac and co-workers²⁹ and by Coates and Sowerby³⁰.

We have successfully accomplished³¹ a total synthesis of (\pm)-isokhusimone (**57**) (Scheme 8) from the easily accessible indane derivative **59**. Ar₁-5 cyclisation of **59** provided the tricyclic dienone **60** in high yield. Reduction of **60** with NaBH₄ under controlled conditions gave the alcohol **61** which was converted into the tetrahydropyranyl ether **62**. Hydroxylation of **62** with OsO₄ from the less hindered *exo*-face furnished the *cis*-diol **63** which was converted into the

Scheme 8

monomesylate **64**. The bonds a and b of **64** being antiperiplanar, the monomesylate rearranged smoothly on treatment with base (1 equiv. of *t*-BuOK) to afford **65** which after deprotection of the THP group gave the keto-alcohol **66** as the sole product. Treatment of **66** with MeMgI furnished the diol **67**. The stereostructure of the corresponding monoacetate **68** was established by X-ray crystallography. Dehydration of **68** gave **69** which on hydrolysis furnished the known²⁶ alcohol **70**. Swern oxidation of **70** afforded (\pm)-isokhusimone (**57**). The spectral data of **70** and **57** were in excellent agreement with those reported in the literature.

Recently, we have accomplished highly stereocontrolled synthesis^{32,33} of the bridged tricyclic compounds **71**³³ and **72**³² as potential intermediates for the synthesis of zizaene (**55**) and khusimone (**56**), respectively, involving aryl par-

ticipated cyclisation as a key reaction. The synthesis of the ketone **71** constitutes³⁰ a formal total synthesis of (\pm)-zizaene (**55**) (Scheme 9). The transformation of the olefin **72** into

Scheme 9

(\pm)-khusimone (**56**) has recently been successfully accomplished in our laboratories. The details of our synthesis of (\pm)-norzizanone (**71**) and (\pm)-khusimone (**56**) will be reported elsewhere.

Synthesis of potential intermediates for tricyclic sesquiterpenes :

We have extended our studies on aryl participated cyclisations involving indane and tetrahydronaphthalene derivatives to provide functionalised tricyclic intermediates (Scheme 10) suitable for the synthesis of the tricyclic sesquiterpenes α -cedrene (**41**), silphinine (**73**), and clovene (**3**).

The diketones **74**³⁴, **75**³⁴ and **76**³⁵ incorporating requisite structural features are expected to serve as useful intermediates for the synthesis of the sesquiterpenes **41**, **73** and **3**, respectively.

Application of aryl participated cyclisations to the synthesis of diterpenoid natural products

Total synthesis of (\pm)-pisiferic acid and related diterpenes :

The abietane-type diterpene acid (\pm)-pisiferic acid (**77**) was isolated³⁶ from the leaves of *Chamaecyparis pisifera* along with several closely related diterpenes. Pisiferic acid (**77**) incorporates a *trans*-fused octahydrophenanthrene skeleton with an angular carboxyl substituent. Earlier methodologies^{37,38} for the synthesis of pisiferic acid and related diterpenes most commonly employed transannular oxidation of the angular methyl group as the key reaction. We have for the first time achieved³⁹ a stereocontrolled total

Scheme 10

synthesis of (±)-pisiferic acid using an aryl participated diazoketone cyclisation strategy. Our work also constitutes formal total synthesis of the naturally occurring diterpenes *O*-methylpisiferic acid (78) and methyl pisiferate (79) (*vide infra*).

Our synthesis of (±)-pisiferic acid is outlined in Scheme 11. The ester **80** was prepared from 6-isopropyl-7-methoxy-1-tetralone involving a Reformatsky reaction with methyl 4-bromocrotonate followed by catalytic hydrogenation. Oxidation of **80** with CrO₃ gave the keto-ester **81**. Bromination of **81** furnished the bromoketone **82** which on dehydrobromination followed by methylation provided the ester **83**. This was converted into the tetrahydrophenanthrene derivative **84** by treatment with MeMgI followed by an intramolecular cyclisation (PPA). Oxidation of **84** with pyridinium chlorochromate yielded the ketone **85**. The formyl deriva-

Scheme 11

tive of **85** was treated with alkaline H₂O₂ followed by CH₂N₂ to give the diester **86** which on partial hydrolysis afforded the half-acid ester **87**. Aryl participated cyclisation of the corresponding diazomethyl ketone **88** in the presence of TFA furnished the enedione **89** (62%) which on catalytic hydrogenation provided the *trans*-fused keto-ester **90** as the sole product. The stereostructure of **90** was established by X-ray crystallography. Desulfurisation of the corresponding thioketal **91** with Raney nickel furnished the ester **92** which was converted³⁹ into (±)-pisiferic acid (**77**) in high yield by treatment with AlBr₃ in the presence of EtSH. Hydrolysis of the ester **92** with *t*-BuOK in DMSO yielded⁴⁰ the diterpene **78** while treatment of **92** with AlCl₃ in the presence of EtSH at 0° afforded³⁷ the diterpene **79**.

Synthesis of potential intermediates for diterpenes and diterpene alkaloids :

The tetracyclic amine **93** served as the key intermediate in the total syntheses^{41,42} of the complex diterpene alkaloids atisine and veatchine. The same synthon **93** was also utilised in the total synthesis⁴³ of gibberellin A₁₅. In connection with our studies on aryl participated cyclisations, we have accomplished⁴⁴ a stereocontrolled synthesis of the bridged tetracyclic ketone **102** (Scheme 12) which is easily convertible⁴⁵ into the tetracyclic amine **93**.

The ketone **94**, prepared from 1,7-dimethoxynaphthalene

Scheme 12

was converted into the corresponding trimethylsilylcyano-hydrin derivative. Treatment of this with POCl₃ and pyridine followed by dehydrogenation provided the aromatic nitrile **95**. Reductive methylation of the corresponding methyl ester **96** in liquid ammonia followed by catalytic hydrogenation afforded the ester **97**. Saponification of **97** yielded **98** which was converted into the diazomethyl ketone **99**. Aryl participated cyclisation of **99** in the presence of TFA at -20° furnished the desired enedione **100** together with the rearranged product **101** which could be easily separated from **100**. Catalytic hydrogenation of **100** proceeded stereoselectively with uptake of 3 moles of hydrogen to afford **102** in near quantitative yield. The structure of **102** was confirmed through comparison with an authentic⁴⁵ sample.

Earlier in this laboratory, the bicyclic enone **103** was efficiently converted⁴⁶ (Scheme 13) into the tricyclic keto-ester **105** involving Robinson annulation [103 → 104] as the key step. We envisaged that similar transformations of the tricyclic enones **106**, **107** and **108** into the tetracyclic

Scheme 13

diterpenes phyllocladene (**109**), hibaene (**110**) and atisirene (**111**) would be possible involving Robinson annulation as the key reaction (Scheme 14). For entry into the ring sys-

Scheme 14

tems of the tetracyclic diterpenes **109**, **110** and **111**, we have synthesised^{47,48} the tricyclic enediones **114**, **115** and **116** involving aryl participated cyclisation as the key reaction as

Scheme 15

shown in Scheme 15. The transformation of **112** into **117** en route to phyllocladene (**109**) has been successfully accomplished⁴⁹ in our laboratories (Scheme 16).

Scheme 16

Our studies on aryl participated cyclisations have provided expedient pathways to the tetracyclic compounds **118**,⁵⁰ **119**⁵¹ and **120**⁴⁴ (Scheme 17) which are related to the aphidicolane – stemodane group of diterpenoids.

Ghatak and his co-workers in our laboratories have extensively investigated⁵²⁻⁵⁴ intramolecular alkylations of

Scheme 17

diazomethyl ketones towards the synthesis of complex diterpenoids. Their studies have provided facile synthetic routes to a variety of complex polycyclic natural products. A few unusual rearrangements have also been discovered during those studies.

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